

Synthesis and Characterisation of μ -Oxobis[oxotetrachloro-rhenates (VI)]

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(Ph_4As)₂Re₂O₈Cl₆ and (Tz)₂Re₂O₈Cl₆ have been prepared by the reduction of perrhenate with acetyl chloride and characterised on the basis of chemical analysis, spectral, magnetic moment and conductivity studies.

VERY few oxo-bridged complexes of Re(IV), Re(V) and Re(VI) are known. Rhenium(IV) forms $\text{K}_4[\text{Re}_2\text{O}_8\text{Cl}_6]$ in the reduction of potassium perrhenate by iodide in hydrochloric acid solution¹. For Re(VI) and Re(V), only μ -oxodioxo-complexes are known. $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_8\text{Cl}_4(\text{py})_4$ and $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_8\text{Cl}_4(\text{bipy})_2$ are prepared by reacting ReCl_5 with the ligand in wet acetone² or by reacting ReOCl_4 or $\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2$ with the ligand in benzene³. $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_8(\text{R}_2\text{dtc})_4$ complexes are obtained by reacting $\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2$ or $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_8\text{Cl}_4(\text{py})_4$ with the dithiocarbamate ligand⁴. $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_8\text{Cl}_4(\text{en})_2$ is obtained by standing $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{en})_2^+$ in hydrochloric acid⁵. The $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_8\text{Cl}_6^{2-}$ anion is precipitated by partial hydrolysis on exposing chloroform solution of ReOCl_4 and Ph_4As^+ or Et_4N^+ chloride to atmosphere⁶. $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_8\text{Cl}_6(\text{ReO}_8\text{Cl})_2$ is obtained⁷ by uv irradiation of a mixture of ReOCl_4 , $\text{ReOCl}_4 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})$ and ReO_2Cl .

We report here the synthesis of (Ph_4As)₂Re₂O₈Cl₆ and (Tz)₂Re₂O₈Cl₆ compounds in good yield from potassium perrhenate.

Experimental

Materials: KReO_4 (J.M.) was dried at 120°. Ph_4AsCl (Fluka) and 2,3,5-triphenyl tetrazolium chloride (Sisco) were dried over P_2O_5 *in vacuo*. All the solvents and other chemicals were thoroughly dried by suitable methods. All experiments were carried out in glove box under oxygen-free dry nitrogen. Petroleum ether (60-80) was used. AcOH-HCl was prepared by saturating acetic acid with hydrogen chloride gas.

Preparation of the compounds:

Tetraphenylarsonium salt: KReO_4 (0.400 g) was taken in acetyl chloride (10 ml) and kept for 40 hr. Ph_4AsCl (0.620 g) in AcOH-HCl (10 ml) was added to the red Re(VI) solution after filtration. The dark red precipitate formed was immediately filtered, washed with AcOH-HCl and dried *in vacuo* over NaOH for 6 hr.

Tetrazolium salt: To the clear red Re(VI) solution obtained as above were added 2,3,5-triphenyl tetrazolium chloride (0.482 g) in AcOH-HCl (5 ml) and acetyl chloride (5 ml). Shiny brown precipitate

was obtained, filtered, washed with AcOH-HCl and dried as above.

The yield is 85% in both the cases.

Elemental analyses and physical measurements: After alkaline peroxide fusion of the sample, rhenium was determined as tetraphenylarsonium perrhenate⁸ and chloride as silver chloride⁹. The uv-vis spectra of solution were taken on a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer using 1 cm silica cell. Infrared spectra were recorded with Beckman IR-20. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined by the Gouy method, packing the tubes under dry nitrogen in glove box. Molar conductances were measured with a Philips bridge PR950J/90 using a dip type microcell having a cell constant of 0.14 cm^{-2} .

Results and Discussion

The red and brown compounds are soluble in dichloromethane, acetone, nitromethane, acetonitrile but insoluble in benzene and carbon tetrachloride. The present method enables preparation of Ph_4As^+ and tetrazolium salts of $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_8\text{Cl}_6^{2-}$ ion in a very pure form. Their molar conductances, 150-180 $\text{ohm}^{-2}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$ in nitromethane, support their formulations as 2 : 1 electrolytes¹⁰. Their chemical analyses and other physical data are presented in Table 1.

The electronic spectra of the compounds in dichloromethane show the same peaks of Re(VI) as $\text{Re}^{\text{VI}}\text{OCl}_4^-$ and also confirm the hexavalent state of rhenium. The ϵ 's of the peaks are similar but less than those⁹ of $\text{Ph}_4\text{AsReOCl}_4$.

The ir spectrum of the tetrazolium salt is reproduced in Fig. 1; that of the Ph_4As^+ salt shows the same features. The $\nu(\text{Re}=\text{O})$ bands are listed in Table 1. Rest of the bands in the region 4000-400 cm^{-1} are due to the cation. The compounds show three main bands at ~ 970 , ~ 950 and ~ 910 cm^{-1} . In case of the arsonium salt, the two higher energy bands are split probably due to site symmetry. The above data suggest two possible structures I and II for the $[\text{Re}_2\text{O}_8\text{Cl}_6]^{2-}$ ion with *cis* and *trans* terminal oxygens respectively to the oxo-bridge between the two rhenium atoms. A

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF μ -OXOBIS [OXOTETRACHLORORHENATES(VI)]

Compound and colour	% Re	% Cl	λ_{max} nm (ε)				$\nu(\text{Re}=\text{O})^c$ (cm ⁻¹)	$\nu(\text{Re}-\text{O}-\text{Re})^c$ (cm ⁻¹)	Δ_o^d	μ_{eff}^e (B.M.)
(Ph ₂ As) ₂ Re ₂ O ₂ Cl ₆ Dark red	24.87 (25.30) ^a	18.47 (19.31)	300 (1971)	440 (908)	550 (160)	900 (18)	935 m, 945 m 968 w, 955 w	905 s	190	1.46
(Tz) ₂ Re ₂ O ₂ Cl ₆ Brown	28.15 (28.59)	21.20 (21.82)	300	440	550 (117)	880 (6)	950 m, 975 m	915 s	176	1.48

a—values in parentheses are Calcd. values.
 b—in dichloromethane.
 c—in nujol.
 d—molar conductance, ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹.
 e—at R. T.

Fig. 1. IR spectra (a) (TZ)Cl, (b) (TZ)₂[Re₂O₂Cl₆] in nujol.

linear bridge is assumed as it would permit better Re-O π -bonding than the bent one.

Structure

Structure II was assigned to the mauve products obtained by Brisdon and Edwards⁶ on the basis of a doublet at 970 cm⁻¹ suggesting a bond with terminal oxygen and a band at 730 cm⁻¹ suggesting Re-O-Re, the lower value for the frequency indicating terminal oxygens in *trans* positions. This is supported by the weak paramagnetism of the compounds.

The antisymmetric Re-O-Re frequency for structure I is expected in the general range of frequencies, i.e., 800-950 cm⁻¹, found for oxygen-bridged halocomplexes⁶. Also, the reduced symmetry

of the unit of the dimer might lead to splitting of degenerate frequencies and appearance of forbidden frequencies. So the bands at ~970 cm⁻¹ and at ~950 cm⁻¹ of the red to brown dimers can be assigned to the bond with terminal oxygen and the strong and somewhat broader band at ~910 cm⁻¹ to Re-O-Re bonding having terminal oxygens in *cis* positions. It is, therefore, reasonable to suggest that these dimers have structure I. They show slightly reduced paramagnetism compared to Re^{VI}OCl₅ ion^{6,11}, due possibly to the exchange interactions. The antiferromagnetic coupling is weaker than that found for the *trans*-isomer by Brisdon and Edwards⁶. The presence of oxygens in *cis* positions to the bridge seems to weaken the antiferromagnetic coupling.

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